

ABSTRACT

Automatic Foot Spa Machine Controller

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Beauty salon industry offers new trends and opportunities to share the concepts of technology integration to foot spas a process in the field of Nail Care Services which leads to the idea of designing and fabricating a machine features that brings significant benefits to the end user and the service provider. This research aims to design, construct and evaluate the acceptability level of the automatic foot spa machine controller in terms of functionality, durability, safety and ease to operate. The uniqueness of this study is the use of photocell as the sensor that automatically turns on the water inlet valve connected to the contactor that makes the timer works as well as the machine functions and drain system.

The Research and Development (R& D) method were used in constructing and fabricating as well as descriptive method for data analysis and interpretation. The machine was evaluated by experts composed of five (5) teachers, ten (10) Nail Care students from Camarines Sur National High School and ten (10) practitioners. The researcher used weighted mean as statistical treatment.

The device level of acceptability in terms of functionality obtained an average weighted mean of 4.9 (highly acceptable); along its durability an average weighted mean of 4.7 (highly acceptable); along safety an average weighted mean of 4.7 (highly acceptable); and ease of usage got an average weighted mean of 4.6 (highly acceptable). The general average weighted mean of the Automatic Foot Spa Machine Controller was 4.7 with verbal interpretation of highly acceptable.

Results implies that the device was very convenient, unique, highly acceptable and recommended to be use in rendering foot spa service because it makes the process easier, safer and faster that brings out the importance of work simplification.

Keywords: Automatic, Foot Spa Machine Controller, Photocell